

Using of Positive Psychotherapy Narratives at School

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Abstract—In this study, how affects the narrative of Positive Psychotherapy which is named “The Three Small Gold Statues” the adolescent’s perception is investigated. The sample included 90 adolescents who were high school students. Firstly the narrative was read. Then three questions which were about the narrative were asked. The questions were: What kind of things did you recall what kind of results did you conclude, and also how could you use this narrative in your real life problems. Responds were analyzed by content analysis method. According to research findings the narrative had a great effect for adolescent perceptions, and also the tale could be used at school counselling programs.

Keywords—Narrative, Positive Psychotherapy, School Counselling Programs

I. INTRODUCTION

In their life, humans have listened to or narrated or wrote narratives many times. Some of them applied to the narratives for live narration, some of them used it for adding something from real life to their writing, and some of them also used it for giving advice to readers. The fact that they are important motivation resources lies behind the intense usage of narratives by humans [1]. Thus, the narratives are not limited to ordinary people’s use only. Moreover, because of its many functions it is used scientifically in many discipline field such as family therapy, anthropology, ethnology, philosophy and psychology.

The questions such as what is a narrative, what kinds of factors are included in it are very important. In a narrative there should be at least two past simple tense phrase [2]. A narrative consists of many items [3]. These are actor, action, aim or intent, scenario and the means used for reaching aims. In addition to these, both the activities directed to aims and the moral values arranging humans relationship take place in narratives. Not only is cognition stated but also emotions also are taken into consideration in the narratives.

A narrative has a lot of functions [1]. Firstly they provide introjection of social events, states and actions. Hence, they realize the construction of the means shared socially. Narratives contribute to the deciding skills of individuals greatly [4]. Narratives also contribute to regulation of emotions [5]. Narratives at the same time improve problem solving and planning skills [6].

With respect to counselling and therapy narratives are used in the fields of both Narrative Therapy and Positive

Psychotherapy. But there are some differences in their usage. Narrative Therapy is based on the social construction. The human’s life experiences are their narratives. In this perceptions and the meanings of perceptions form the constructions of narratives. Narrative Therapy never see a human as a problem but takes him in hand as being having problems.

The aim of the Narrative Therapy is to help reconstruction of problematic life narratives of clients and to help to construct the life narratives they wish [7]. Narrative Therapy is carried out many areas and results in success. For instance successful results have been observed in the study fulfilled with HIV patients [8] the sexually abused children [9], and the guilty children who can not control their anger [10].

Positive Psychotherapy is based on balance model. Individuals cope with the confictions they face by their bodies, their achievements, their social contact and fantasy. The aim of Positive Psychotherapy is to widen the opportunity with which he copes the confictions. In that view, the therapy has five stages; observation stage, inventory stage, stative encouragement stage, verbalization stage, the stage of widening the targets [11].

There are many aims of using narrative in Positive Psychotherapy. Firstly, narratives constitute identification state for clients. The richness of images in narratives get the content of narratives approached of ego and provide that the readers identify with these images more easily. Narratives are as models. They reveal conflictual situation and present probable solutions. Narratives help client face their confictions. Because of the fact that they are interpreted differently in different situation by clients and transferred to many daily life areas, they function as storeys. Narratives at the same time are transporter of tradition which exist at this time. Due to the fact that they emerge opposite ideas, narratives provide clients with different points of views. Thus, the changing of client’s perspective can be more easy via these narratives [11].

In Narrative Therapy the problems of the client are taken in hand, and also for solution to the problems alternative life styles state the wanted narrative. On the other hand, in Positive Psychotherapy narratives are used constructively at a suitable time. While in Narrative Therapy the narrative of human from the whole process of therapy, in Positive Psychotherapy narratives are as means used for functioning of the therapy process.

In the literature, school counseling curricula based on narrative have been prepared. For example some researcher, have prepared school counseling program by making use of the narratives which take place in school books [12]. The aim of this application is to improve the deciding and learning

skills of primary school children. As a result, positive results have been taken.

Adolescence is a stage at which physical, social, cognitive and moral development occurs. Although identification development lasts for life span, the adolescent face identification development intensively [13]. By forming identification and social cognition they gain, adolescent realizes socially reality easily [14]. With aging the adolescent began to spend most of his time afar from his family [15]. Thus, adolescent gets social development accelerated. With identification development, adolescent gets ready for adulthood of future life [13]. Positive Psychotherapy narratives can present different perspective views to the adolescent changing and developing. Hence, the adolescent could think about his development. He can understand himself and his life more better by interpreting for himself and his life.

II. METHOD

A. Procedure and Participants

The main aim of this study is that Positive Psychotherapy narratives are used in school counseling programs. Thus, the effect of Positive Psychotherapy narrative “ The Three Small Gold Statues” on adolescent perceptions were investigated. The narrative is this:

“ One day a king wanted to measure the intellect and reasoning of the neighbor king and his people. Therefore, he sent to the neighbor king 3 small golden statues each of which had the same appearance and weight. The thing that the neighbor king would do was to find the most valuable one. The neighbor king put his assembly together and couldn't find any small differences among the statues by looking them. Even the most intelligent people of the Kingdom was ready to guarantee that there were no differences among them. That there weren't any people who could evaluate the differences among the statues became a source of grief. All of the people in Kingdom joined in this event and did what they could do. When they were about to lose their hope, a young man sent a news from the jail. He stated that he could determine the differences among them on condition that they gave permission. Accordingly, the king got the young man to bring his palace and gave him the statues. The young man examined the statues carefully and saw a hole in the in the ears of each one. By continuing his research, he pushed silver cable into the ears of each one. In the first statue the silver cable emerged from the mouth of its; in the second, from the ear of its; in the third one, from the core of its. In this case he thought some and said to the king:Oo sacred king! I think that the answer of this riddle is in front of you like a clear book. We need to read this book only. As you see, likewise people are different from each other, these three statues also different from each other. The first statue reminds us of the people who say the thing they heard to the others immediately. The second statue looks like people who don't take the words into consideration. The third statue resembles the people hiding the things they heard and behaving according to them. My lord, by taking this features into consideration you can decide

which is valuable from the statues. Which one do you want a confidant for you? The people who don't hide anything on their own? The people who don't appreciate your words pretending they are soap foam? Or the people who hide your words safely.”

90 adolescents 8 of whom are male and 82 of whom are female, the ages 15 (42 persons) and 16 (48) persons take participate in this study from the school Ankara Pursaklar Y.Kemal and M. Sönmez Vocational Health High School.

Firstly, the narrative “ The Three Small Gold Statues” was read out for students by counselor. After that, the students were asked three questions: Why is this narrative important for you or what did it remind you? What are the results you conclude from this narrative? How do you apply this narrative to your real life problem or problems? Explain it by giving an example. Responds were analyzed by content analysis method. In the analysis of data the sentences were used as units of analysis and the analysis of emotional expect wasn't considered.

III. RESULTS

The results depending upon the things that the narrative reminds adolescents: In the total 103 sentences attributed to things of which the narrative remind the adolescents were obtained. The sentences obtained were classified under 6 categories. 35 sentences are related to individual differences (it is important because it express that each person is different from others), 27 sentences are related peer relationship formation (it is important because it helps choosing friends), 16 sentences are related different reminiscence (it is important because it express that we must know our responsibilities), 11 sentences are related to questioning the daily life problems by focusing the example (it is important because three small gold statues are different from others), 8 sentences are related reliance (trust) (it is important because it express trust to people), 6 sentences are related to know people (it is important because it express that the people are not the people seeming outside (appearance is deceptive).

When examined the results concluded from the narratives that 113 sentences were obtained in six categories. The dispersion of the results that 32 sentences are the result of knowing people (I understood that before deciding something we must know people), 32 sentences are the result of formation peer relationship (I understood that we must choose our friends carefully), 20 sentences are the result of concealing secrets (I understood that we don't share our secrets with every people), 17 sentences are the result of interpersonal trust (reliance) (I understood that we don't trust every people), 8 sentences are the result of communication with people(I understood that we have to listen to people communicated with us carefully) , and 4 sentences are the result of depending upon focusing example (I understood that the king is measuring the three people's knowledge).

When we consider the narrative with respect to applying it in life, we can understand that 58 students of 90 applied the narrative to the life by self disclose but 32 of them only applied it without self-disclose.

IV. DISCUSSION

By looking of the study, it is possible that the application is evaluated with respect to social and cognitive development, intimate relationships, Positive Psychotherapy and school counseling programs.

Adolescents, in relation to children spend much of their time in social relationships. In this process they know themselves and others [15]. According to the results of recognize the research adolescents attribute narrative largely to individual differences. They concluded some results for knowing people from the narrative. The results shows that adolescent interact more socially.

It is important for an adolescent that he should have perspective taking by solving problems he encounters [16]., by constructing his relationships, by forming his individual borders like this, by collapsing egocentrism of adolescent, the perspectives of others have great importance [17]. The fact that adolescents conclude results concerning accepting individual differences of themselves and recognizing others may be the extension of perspective taking by means of narrative.

Adolescent abstracted results concerning constructing of peer relationships. A reason for this situation may be the fact that they have the ability of understanding intimate relationships now. The adolescent experiencing cognitive development became to understanding intimate experience and intimate interaction [18]. The development of abstract reasoning during the stage of adolescence enables adolescents to understand the importance of intimate friendships. In their context is it concluded that narrative can be used of formation of peer relationships.

There are three main features of intimate relationships. Reliance (trust), attachment and affection [18]. Reliance means that individuals have intimate relationships to know what each other want for themselves. The individuals trusting each other are aware the fact that the other one doesn't damage to them and they don't deceive each other. It is important that narrative reminds adolescents of reliance and that adolescents abstracted results concerning reliance in relationships from the narrative. This case displays that adolescent recognizes one of the important feature of intimate relationships.

One of the most important features of Positive Psychotherapy is that clients develop the ability of helping on their own. In this context, the majority of adolescents disclose themselves. They use the results they concluded from the narrative to solve their problems. Thus, Psychotherapy narrative enable the adolescent to help on their own. And also the self-disclose of adolescents on their own, may be a result of mirror effect [19].

When viewed with respect to school counseling programs the fact that narratives take place in programs may be quite functional in school counselor interact with one person during an hour via individual counseling. It may not be possible that narrative replaces the consultant. However, it's important to use narrative in school counseling programs on the basis at the fact that it helps most of the adolescents in the point of

determining the adolescents who need the help of school counselling service.

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